

A STUDY ON PROBLEMS OF PARENTAL CARE ON MENTALLY RETARDED CHILDREN IN TERMS OF SOCIAL SUPPORT WITH REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE

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Abstract:

Caring for mentally retarded children is a very important task of parents and it is most importantly for the mothers than fathers. There is more strain caused to the mothers because all the care aspects of mentally retarded children will be met mothers. This study investigates the specific difficulties faced by parents in Coimbatore in providing physical care for their mentally retarded children. The research examine daily care giving activities such as hygiene management, feeding, mobility assistance, and medical care, highlighting the physical, emotional, and financial burdens experienced by parents. Thanks to the human genome it is producing 2 to 3% of the mentally retarded as against a good percent of normal humans. This low percent is not only due to genetic errors but also due to so many infectious diseases that the human embryo faces from the day of fertilization or due to epigenetic factors on the chromosomes of the male and female gametes. The findings emphasize the need for targeted intervention programs, such as specialized caregiver training and improved healthcare services, to alleviate the physical care giving burden.

Introduction

Parents of mentally retarded children are known to experience many kinds“ unusual impacts from the competitive society from time to time to manage and adjust to the best of their abilities. The impact includes, sad feeling of parents, depressed at various stages of child’s life with experiences of many other emotional reactions. Their social life is often affected without much recreation and leisure for many positive opportunities and activities to score for their credit. At such an unimaginable rate of changes in human genomes much concerned with the neurons of

the brain and its network several sense, mis-sense and non- sense mutations are unavoidable giving rise to changes of all dimensions producing rulers on the top to an idiot on the lower rung of the ladder of human development. Researchers has also indicated that greater the number of unmet needs , greater the number of emotional and physical problems reported by parents.(Dunst & Leet 1987,Vence and Cooper 1986), (Kasuya, Polgar-Bailey, Takeuchi, 2000) reveled that“ a multidimensional response to physical, psychological, emotional, social and financial stressors usually associated with the experience of caring” Objective burden includes measurable effects such as economic burden, caregivers“ loss of work, social and leisure activities, household disruptions such as child care, restrictions on relationships within and outside the family etc.

Problem Statement:

The care of mentally retarded children presents a unique and multifaceted challenge for parents, who often bear the primary responsibility for the child's physical, emotional, and social well-being. In Coimbatore, a city with a growing population and diverse socio-economic landscape, the burden on parents can be particularly overwhelming due to a range of factors including social stigma, limited access to specialized healthcare, and inadequate support systems. Parents of mentally retarded children in Coimbatore frequently face significant difficulties that impact their quality of life and the well-being of their children. These challenges are not only limited to the direct care of the child but extend to emotional and psychological stress, financial strain, and social isolation. The lack of adequate institutional support, coupled with societal misconceptions about mental retardation, exacerbates the situation, making it difficult for parents to provide optimal care for their children.

Scope of the Study:

The study is geographically focused on Coimbatore, a major city in Tamil Nadu, India. Coimbatore is known for its diverse population and varying levels of access to healthcare, education, and social services. By focusing on this specific region, the study aims to explore how the local context influences the experiences of parents caring for mentally retarded children. This regional focus allows for an in-depth analysis of the available resources, cultural attitudes, and community support systems that are unique to Coimbatore.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Garcia, M. F., & Torres, F. M. (2015) examined the role of healthcare providers in supporting parents of children with intellectual disabilities, using a sample of 190 parents. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to assess parents' experiences and perceptions of healthcare support. The analysis found that strong, consistent connections with healthcare professionals significantly enhanced parental confidence and reduced caregiving challenges.

Hanson, M. J., & Hanline, M. F. (2014) conducted a study examining the impact of social support systems on parents of children with intellectual disabilities, involving a sample of 190 parents. Utilizing a combination of quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, the researchers assessed the structure and effectiveness of various social support systems, including formal and informal networks. Their analysis demonstrated that structured social support significantly alleviates caregiver stress and enhances overall well-being. Parents who engaged with well-organized support systems reported lower levels of stress and higher levels of emotional and psychological resilience. The study underscores the importance of robust and organized social support systems in mitigating the challenges faced by caregivers and improving their quality of life.

Objectives of the Study

- To investigate the problems of parental care on mentally retarded children of the respondents.
- To study the relations between problems of parental care on mentally retarded children of the respondents.
- To examine problems of parental care on mentally retarded children as significant predictors of the respondents.

Methodology

This study, which focuses on the problems of parental care for mentally retarded children in Coimbatore, a descriptive research design has been selected. This design is particularly well-suited for the study as it allows for a detailed examination and documentation of the various challenges faced by parents. In this study, the universe consists of parents caring for mentally retarded children in Coimbatore. The sampling technique employed in this study is probability

sampling, which guarantees that every individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected. Out of the total population of 877 individuals, a sample of 400 participants was chosen for the study. The selection process was conducted using **simple random sampling**, specifically the **lottery method**. The complete list of individuals was obtained from the District Differently Abled Welfare Office Coimbatore, and the sampling process was carefully executed to ensure an unbiased selection.

The researcher used questionnaire for collecting data from the respondents which has two sections. Data for the study were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data were obtained directly from respondents through a structured questionnaire, ensuring the collection of firsthand information crucial to the research. Secondary data were gathered from various sources, including newspapers, magazines, journals, and books. This blend of primary and secondary data provided a robust and comprehensive foundation for analyzing the study's research questions and objectives.

Various statistical tests were used to analyze the collected data. The tools are presented below:-

- Mean and standard deviation
- Simple Percentage
- Chi-square
- T-test
- F-Test or ANOVA
- Co-efficient of correlation
- Multiple Regression

Results and Discussion

The personal profile of parents is a critical aspect of this study as it directly correlates with the quality of care they can provide to their mentally retarded children. Parents come from a variety of backgrounds, each facing unique challenges in caregiving based on their personal circumstances.

Level of Overall physical care

Majority 65 % of the respondents had moderate overall level of physical care.

Level of Behaviour problems

Majority 65 % of the respondents have moderate level of behaviour problems.

Level of Social support

Nearly 57.5 % of the respondents have moderate level of social support.

Level of Burden of parents

Majority 61.4 % of the respondents have moderate burden of parents.

Level of Adjustment of parents

Majority 64 % of the respondents have moderate adjustment of parents

IMPLICATIONS FOR SOCIAL WORK PRACTICE

The challenges faced by parents or caregivers of mentally retarded children present a significant area of concern for social work practice. As professionals working closely with vulnerable populations, social workers play a crucial role in alleviating the emotional, social, financial, and psychological burdens experienced by these families. To address the complex issues arising from parental care for children with intellectual disabilities, social work practice must adapt a holistic and multi-dimensional approach.

CONCLUSION

Despite these challenges, there is hope in the form of support systems, policy interventions, and societal change. Strengthening family support, offering financial assistance, enhancing access to special education and health services, and addressing mental health needs are critical strategies for alleviating the burden on these parents. Additionally, public awareness and the reduction of stigma are essential for creating a more inclusive society that embraces individuals with intellectual disabilities and their families.